

A Story about Ruin: Biden's Effort to Integrate the Middle East

Waleed Hazbun

Waleed Hazbun teaches international relations and US foreign policy in the Middle East at the University of Alabama. He is currently (2024-25) a visiting scholar at the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Thessaloniki, Greece.

In his spring 2021 speech, “A Foreign Policy for the American People,” Secretary of State Antony Blinken outlined the new administration’s strategic vision. Responding to the experience of the pandemic and Donald Trump’s America First populism, Blinken (2021) sought to connect US policy goals to domestic concerns about economic recovery and protecting democracy. The Middle East is mentioned only in passing and Israel not at all. The *Interim National Security Strategic Guidance* published at the time emphasized the coming struggle of democracies against autocracies (Biden 2021). It includes Biden’s mantra about “our ironclad commitment to Israel’s security” and the US goal of seeking Israel’s “integration with its neighbors” (Biden 2021, 11). It also warns, “We do not believe that military force is the answer to the region’s challenges, and we will not give our partners in the Middle East a blank check to pursue policies at odds with American interests and values” (Biden 2021, 11), but appears to refer to Saudi Arabia, not Israel.

While the Middle East was not expected to be a major focus of US foreign policy, nearly four years later – with over 1000 Israelis and 50,000 Palestinians killed, the military capacity of Hizballah decimated, and the Iran-backed regime of Bashar al Assad in Syria overthrown by (former) Jihadists – President Joe Biden would end his term by boasting

about the “diplomatic and geopolitical opportunities we’ve created” including “a new moment for a more stable, integrated Middle East” (Biden 2025). He declared, “our adversaries and competitors are weaker, and we have not gone to war to make these things happen.” The legacy of the administration’s policy in the Middle East, however, will not likely be defined by this view of artful diplomacy and goals achieved. Rather, its legacy will rest on how Biden’s unconditional backing of Israel in its post-October 7 wars left Gaza in ruins and paved the way for President Donald Trump, soon upon taking office, to call for the ethnic cleansing of the Palestinians.

How did this happen? Alexander Ward’s reporting about the first two years of the Biden administration suggests the limited role the Middle East was expected to play. Ward observes, “The administration didn’t want to get bogged down in the Middle East” (cited in Beck 2024, 20). Ward records a source telling him, “We’re really not going to get involved in Israel–Palestine” (cited in Beck 2024, 20). To the degree they did, they embraced the Abraham Accords and Trump’s pro-Israel shifts while claiming to support a “viable” two-state solution.

Biden’s approach to the Middle East was not one of “retreat.” In November 2021, when

National Security Council coordinator for the Middle East Brett McGurk spoke at the Manama regional security summit, his message was, “The US is not going anywhere.” He outlined a “back to basics” strategy that emphasized strong US security commitments to its traditional regional allies (McGurk 2021). McGurk noted that the US would never again stand by when a “friend” gets exposed to fire, as Saudi Arabia did in 2019. US Central Command announced the maintenance of a strong US military force posture in the region. This approach was expected to contain and deter regional rivals such as Iran, allowing the Biden administration to focus on other regions.

Following Russia’s full-scale invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, the stakes of great power competition rapidly expanded. Biden undertook a high-profile visit to meet Arab leaders in Saudi Arabia, telling them, “We will not walk away and leave a vacuum to be filled by China, Russia, or Iran” (cited in Sanger and Baker 2022). US diplomats and military commanders warned regional allies of the security risks of increasing trade and economic ties to China. The National Security Strategy published in October 2022 declared, “The post-Cold War era is definitively over and a competition is underway between the major powers to shape what comes next” (Biden 2022, 6). But it also noted, “We have too often defaulted to military-centric policies underpinned by an unrealistic faith in force and regime change to deliver sustainable outcomes” and “We will not use our military to change regimes or remake societies” (Biden, 2022, 42, 43).

As US efforts focused on getting Saudi Arabia to sign a normalization agreement with Israel and expanding regional economic and security integration, US National Security Advisor

Jake Sullivan could assess in late September 2023 that “The Middle East region is quieter today than it has been in two decades” (cited in Beckerman 2023). It seems clear the Biden administration was unprepared for the brutal Hamas-led assault into Israel on October 7, 2023, killing over a thousand Israelis and taking over 200 hostages back to Gaza. Mirroring similar shifts after 9/11 and the Soviets’ detonation of their first atomic weapon, US threat perceptions were transformed, leading to a more assertive, and at times reckless, approach.

Israel’s ferocious retaliation against Hamas in Gaza led to the spread of intense regional conflict, exposing the limits of the Biden administration’s approach to the Middle East. The US recommitted to backing Israel militarily and deploying more of its own military assets to the region to deter attacks against US forces and its regional allies. For almost a year, US officials appeared to hope for an end to the hostilities so it might return to promoting regional security and economic integration. But Biden held back from applying the required pressure on Israel to accept a sustained cease-fire while likely violating US law by continuing arms shipments (Borger 2024). US officials took credit for preventing a total Israeli blockage of humanitarian aid to Gaza. Meanwhile, Israel continued its destructive campaign in Gaza with so much unrestrained force and with seeming disregard for the civilian population that it was soon accused of war crimes and genocide (Albanese 2024, Amnesty 2024). The military commanders of Hamas responsible for the October 7 attacks, now dead, were also charged with war crimes and crimes against humanity (International Criminal Court 2024).

Meanwhile, key regional US allies such as Saudi Arabia, Jordan, and Egypt feared the

consequences of Israel's actions for Palestine and the region. The extent of the physical destruction and human suffering in Gaza, as well as parts of Lebanon, horrified Arab societies, fostering networks of Palestinian solidarity and challenging efforts to promote further normalization with Israel (El Kurd 2024). In recent years, less concerned about the threat of Iran, most Arab states have sought to dampen the effects of regional turbulence by limiting their involvement in armed conflicts, de-escalating regional rivalries, and attempting to rebuild political order within war-torn states. While they view Iran as a threat, most Arab states wish to avoid a more polarized region and have sought ties with Israel as part of the broader diversification of their security relationships and arms suppliers. The ongoing conflict, however, forced them to suppress pro-Palestinian demonstrations and strained their relations with Israel by exposing differences over the future of Palestine.

In contrast to the efforts of Arab states, Israel's extensive, multifront military campaign has sought to eliminate the capacities of rival non-state actors and their main state backer, Iran (the so-called "Axis of Resistance"). While waging its campaign against Gaza, Israel also continued bombing sites in Lebanon as well as Hizballah and Iranian targets in Syria and Houthi targets in Yemen. A year later, once the bulk of Hamas's military capacity was eliminated and Gaza laid in ruins, Israel escalated its conflict with Hizballah with an extensive campaign targeting its leadership, weapon stores, supply infrastructure, and eventually people and buildings across Lebanon that Israel viewed as associated with any aspect of Hizballah. With the success of Israel's campaign in Lebanon, the opportunities to advance US goals seemed to change. As *Politico* reported, "Behind the scenes,

Hochstein, McGurk, and other top U.S. national security officials are describing Israel's Lebanon operations as a history-defining moment — one that will reshape the Middle East for the better for years to come" (Banco and Toosi 2024). By the end of 2024, Israel's devastating campaign had eliminated what Hizballah had long touted as its deterrent capability, debilitated it as an organization, and inflicted so much damage on Lebanon and its people that the group agreed to a ceasefire before there was one in Gaza. As a result, Iran has been forced to reconsider its forward defense strategy and might consider the nuclear option. Responding to the strategic failure and trauma of October 7, Israel not only claimed to restore deterrence by denial but to drastically shift the regional balance of power, enabling a new regional order based on Israel's regional military dominance (Rachman 2024).

With the success of Israel's military campaigns and the rapid collapse of the Assad regime in Syria, in early 2025, the outgoing Biden administration spoke about the new opportunities to forge a "more integrated region and security architecture" created by the shift in the regional balance of power (Blinken 2025). But such efforts fail to recognize how these states lack a common understanding of regional security and differ sharply with Israel and the US about the terms for Palestinian security. While the US has insisted on an Israel-centered approach to regional security, such a vision is likely unsustainable even with expanded normalization agreements. Israel continues to maintain its own exclusive security concerns and strategic approach, leading it to reject Palestinian self-determination, seek to maximize its regional military dominance and deny accusations of genocide. More broadly, the US-backed devastation to Palestine, as well as

Lebanon, might leave a long-lasting mark on the political perspectives of Arab societies, posing challenges to normalization as well as to the US role in the region and regimes dependent on it for security. The most immediate consequence of Biden's failure to balance a focus on Israel's security and its war effort with recognition of Palestinian security was to enable Trump's "'jaw dropping' plan for the United States to 'own' Gaza, remove its Palestinian population and redevelop the enclave as a new Mediterranean Riviera" (DeYoung 2025). The lessons of Gaza echo those of Omar El Akkad's (2018) dystopian novel *American War* that draws on his reporting in the post 9/11 Middle East to imagine a future where southern states have again rebelled against the United States, leading to decades of violence, destruction, and cruelty. As the narrator explains, "This isn't a story about war. It's about ruin." ♦

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